

COOPERATION BETWEEN SCHOOL AND ENTERPRISE AS A MOTIVATION FACTOR IN SCIENCE SUBJECTS

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Abstract. *The paper presents part of the action study conducted within the EU project (ARTiST) in Georgia. The goal of the study was to investigate the impact of cooperation between school and enterprise on students' motivation in science subjects. In 2019, 15 high school students cooperated with the enterprise – Ltd “Schuchmann Wines Georgia,” and completed several activities. As a result, students' motivation increased, positive attitude to technological/technical directions and professional development were established. More research should be conducted to study how successfully cooperation between school and enterprise can be applied by science teachers at secondary schools and higher education institutions.*

Keywords: *cooperation, school, education, science, cooperation*

Introduction

Science, engineering and technology are at the center of the modern public interests. Their development requires the relevant education. An increase of well-being and overtaking local, regional and global challenges are directly related to the natural sciences and technologies . - (The ARTIST Guidebook, 2019)- .The aim of teaching science disciplines is to share the basics of natural science with the student and to develop research skills allowing learning and understanding the universe, being involved in various social activities, to feel responsible for her/himself, the society and the environment (Georgian National Curriculum, 2018-2024).

The modern methods of teaching the natural sciences mean: “ To equip a student with the knowledge and skills that will enable her/him to advance the rapid progress of mankind, to use the achievements of modern science, to become a full member of society. From a passive recipient of knowledge, the student should become an active learner who will be able to use the acquired knowledge for professional success, as well as a benefit for the society,” (Georgian National Curriculum, 2018-2024).

Many researchers in the field of natural science consider that a major problem is - low motivation among students, misconceptions about the relevance of science teaching, and a lack of young people involved in science and engineering. (The ARTIST Guidebook, 2019) Among many factors determining student's interests and motivation, the most important is a teacher and the lesson planned by her/him. It should also be noted that the learning environment and activities carried out by the joint efforts of teacher/school administration are no less meaningful and significant. In addition, the innovations introduced as a result of practical research can impact students' motivation, understanding the importance of studying science subjects, career orientation, and preparation to be employed in the domain of science (Melikishvili, 2003).

The research of school-enterprise cooperation has been actively carried out for several years in different countries. In the field of school-enterprise cooperation, researchers have developed several relevant conceptual frameworks and directions: skills study, technical education, impact on technology reforms, curriculum and apprenticeship (Zhan, 2019).

Cooperation between school and enterprise in Georgian Education system is a relatively new approach. Between 2016-2019, at the Iliia State University, the international project **Action Research To Innovate Science Teaching ARTiST** [www.erasmus-artist.eu], co-funded by the Erasmus programme of European Union was implemented. The project included action research on innovation in science subjects. Within this project, at 12 public and private schools, a science teacher conducted action research on the cooperation between school and enterprise. This paper is a part of the action research carried out at Telavi European School (Georgia) within this project.

Methodology

The goal of our study was to investigate the impact of cooperation between school and enterprise on students' motivation in science subjects. The following research questions guided our study:

1. Did the students' attitude change by the activities implemented within the project?
2. How did students' motivation in science subjects' change after conducting research-based activities?
3. Did gender influence science subject choice?

The following study methods were chosen:

- ❖ Quantitative study – A survey of students' attitudes towards science (in particular, chemistry) using pre- and post-questionnaires;
- ❖ Qualitative study - Student motivation study - focus group interview method;
- ❖ Qualitative study - researcher's journal on students' behavior

Our research methodology was based on action research which aims at introducing an innovative research approach in the field of education. Noffke and Zeichner (Noffke & Zeichner, 1987) describe teacher action research that increases the degree of understanding of classroom issues; improves their attitude towards comprehension and reasoning; changes their values and beliefs; makes theory and practice more consistent; gives a wider / wider range of teaching, school process, and community vision. Action research is cyclical research and, in this case, a combination of science education strategies used by science teachers. (Theories of Development and Learning, 2008).

Participants:

As it was mentioned above, the study was conducted at Telavi European School. Fifteen students (8 girls and 7 boys) of 11th grade were selected, who expressed their desire to participate in the research. Accordingly, their parents were informed and their written consents were received.

Ltd “Schuchmann Wine Georgia” was selected as a partner enterprise. It is a winery that along with wine production has been producing grape seed oil for seven years. The production of grape seed oil became a target for the students. To conduct the research, we developed the action plan in which we wrote down in detail the activities to be carried out by the students throughout the year, as well as the work schedule to be performed by the observer or the teacher. During the project implementation, students completed the following activities:

- obtaining information on oil production technology in general;
- collecting information on grape seed oil;
- visiting the winery.

Students visited the enterprise 4 four times. During the third visit, each student selected an interesting section for her/him and helped the section workers in various activities. Some students conducted interviews with the CEO and staff using questions prepared in advance. After that, students analyzed and evaluated the results of the interviews. All students wrote an essay on the topic "My dream enterprise;" they filled in questionnaires, where they expressed their opinions regarding their future plans, professional interest (in vocational education or higher education), if their interest towards the enterprise changed, their views on the activities in the enterprise and if they had an idea to change anything there. They revealed their opinions on how they could enrich the products of the enterprise. At the school lab, the students produced skin cosmetic ointment and cosmetic soap with grape seed oil.

Research results

The research findings presented in this paper include the quantitative study – pre and post questionnaire. At the beginning of the study, the participants completed the pre-questionnaire form. As part of the project, we assisted students in finding information, sorting and processing material, periodically conducting surveys using pre-designed questionnaires, marking them in the researcher's journal, observing the effectiveness of their work, and if they were developing skills in accordance with the action plan. After the implemented activities, the work was summarized at the internal school conference. After the conference, the post-questionnaires (see Appendix) were distributed among the students involved in the research and filled in.

The results of the survey are presented in Figures -1- . The pre-and post-questionnaires included the following topics:

- Learning chemistry
- Students' interest in learning activities
- How to improve chemistry class
- Students' preferences for the future profession.

We included a total of 4 four closed questions in the pre-questionnaire and 5 questions in the post-questionnaire form. Both questionnaires were completed in class by all students.

At the time of completing the first questionnaire, only 37.5% (15) of the 40 11th graders showed an interest in teaching science. According to the results of the pre-questionnaire, 3 boys (20%) and 4 girls (26.7%) wanted to be employed in the enterprise, while 2 boys (13.3%) and 5 girls (33.3%) liked the direction of technician/technology as a future profession. A focus group of students was formed, who then had to fill in post-questionnaires. The results revealed that 40% of boys and 60% of girls liked the activities in the chemistry lesson. But the approval rate for experiments and practical work showed 40% of girls and 60% of boys. Employment in the enterprise was attractive for 33% (5) of boys and 53% (8) of girls-. (13% abstained from answering) 27% (4) of boys and 53% (8) of girls chose the field of technology as their future profession (20% did not respond). To the question in the pre-questionnaire, 'what would they change in the chemistry lesson?' the following answers were obtained:

- I would conduct experiments that take place in our daily lives and we do not even realize it is related to the teachings of science.

- I would search for more information and get acquainted with the enterprises that operate in our region.

- In an enterprise that is interesting to me, I would go on internships during the summer holidays, etc.

Thus, the students' answers showed that learners wanted to see the link between chemistry/science subject and real-life; how this science subject knowledge was applicable in enterprises. The activities within the research impacted the students' motivation. As a result, students' motivation and interest in science subjects rose (See, Figure 1).

Figure 1. Students' motivation at the beginning and at the end of the project

Discussions

In this paper, we presented the part of the action research conducted within the large-scale international project. This study aimed at examining the impact of cooperation between public school and enterprise on students' motivation and interest in science subjects, specifically chemistry. The study showed that interest towards the carried-out activities among boys and girls was increased in different ways, namely, girls were more motivated than boys. It was clear that the gender thinking and interest of students towards the carried-out activities varied. The boys did not show interest in making cosmetic ointment and soap and their activity was accordingly very low, but instead, they were interested in grape seed oil technology and the technical data of an oil extraction machine. The students liked experiments and practical work, which naturally led to their interest and desire to work in a technological enterprise. At the end of the project, students motivation increased.

Accordingly, by changing the traditional approach to teaching science subjects, students' interest in science changed:

❖ The quality of teaching/learning science subject, as well as students motivation and interest increased;

❖ Positive attitude of students towards professional development was formed;

Conclusion

Activities implemented within the project positively influenced students' motivation and the research-based approach to learning. However, there were a few methodological limitations of the study. The research sample was too small, and it was difficult to find significant relationships from the data and ensure the representative distribution of the population. Future research should consider more carefully the potential effects of the partnership between school and enterprise in the direction of science subjects.

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Appendix

1. Pre-questionnaire form

1. How interesting are the activities of the chemistry lesson for you?
 - a) Very interesting
 - b) Not so interesting
 - c) uninteresting
2. What type of activity is interesting for you?
 - a) Experiments
 - b) Presentations
 - c) Production of some specific product (material)
3. Do you want to change anything while learning chemistry?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No.
 - c) In case of a positive answer, what exactly would you change?
4. I will choose as my future occupation:
 - a) Field of Humanities
 - b) Technical Field
 - c) I have a difficulty to choose

2. Post-questionnaire form

1. How interesting were the activities for you?
 - a) Very interesting
 - b) Not so much interesting
 - c) Uninteresting
2. What type of activity is interesting for you?
 - a) Experiments
 - b) Presentations
 - c) Production of some specific product (material)
3. What did you like from the work carried out by you?
 - a) Preparation of a label
 - b) Labeling
 - c) Bottling and packaging
4. How attractive is for you being employed in such type of an enterprise?
 - a) Working in all type enterprises is interesting
 - b) Working at the laboratory is interesting
 - c) I am not interested in working at such type of enterprise
5. I will choose as my future occupation:
 - a) Field of Humanities
 - b) Technical Field
 - c) I have a difficulty to choose